

Spatial Distribution of Retail Shops along the Yangon-Mandalay Road within Bago City

Min Min Aye Than^{*}, Myint Myint Aye^{**}, Khin Myaung Wai^{***}, Nai Chi Lin^{****}, Mar Mar Khin^{*****}

Abstract

This research paper enquired and analyzed the retail shops along the Yangon-Mandalay Road within Bago City. Population, transportation factors near the markets largely influence the spatial distribution and functions of the retail shops in the study area. Most of the retail shops nearby, locate along the main transportation routes. It represents the shops types and current economic functions on the main road. It reveals cluster of business function of the main road and near the market areas in Bago City. It is studied by using Google Image for base map for the study area and analyzed by ArcMap 10.1 software. And it uses Microsoft Excel to show the diagram and data base. Myoma Market is the mean centre of retail shops and the breaking point of Pyinsi Market. It is also the shortest path and the highest accessibility of the whole Bago City. According to these analyses, retail shops are clustered, particularly along the main roads and in proximity to the markets.

Introduction

Urban or rural have retail shops born up with the increasing population and the needs of the inhabitants of life, distance decay and to use a short span of time. Retail shops affiliated home and using the ground floor on the extensions of the settlement unit. Thus, the distribution pattern of retail shops is concerned by the population density, socio economic condition of the residents and accessibility.

Study Area

The study area is along the Yangon-Mandalay Road within Bago City. It is located in the central part of the City. This part of the City is included in the urban area (municipal area) which is along the Yangon-Mandalay Road within Bago City.

Research Problem

What types and functions of retail shops are along the Yangon-Mandalay Road within Bago City?

Why uneven distributions of retail shops are due to the population, transportation, market, customers and retailers behavior?

Research Hypothesis

- (1) Spatial distribution of market varies in types and function within the study area.
- (2) These variations are transportation routes and distance from the markets.
- (3)

Aim

The main aim of this research is to analyze the spatial distribution of retail shops along the Yangon-Mandalay Road within Bago City, which are uneven because of the population, transportation, market and customer and retailer behaviour.

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Objectives

To study the population, population density and related wards area along the Yangon-Mandaly Road within Bago City

To define the type of retail shops, the number of retail shops, distribution and functions of retail shops along the Yangon-Mandaly Road within Bago City

To analyze the distribution and functions of retail shops are related to the transportation routes and distance from the markets.

Sources of Data and Methodology

Secondary data are derived from official statistics, Google satellite images. Transportation network linkage and analysis were done by Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and Google satellite images. Other secondary data are the Immigration and the Manpower Department original Outline Maps from the Survey Department. Retail shops along the Yangon-Mandaly Road within Bago City is produced by field surveys measuring with the aid of Global Positioning System (GPS) primary data on marketing function and retail shops to use systematic questionnaires. The distributional patterns and functions of retail shops are used by ware of ArcMap 10.1. The degree of concentration and clustering of retail shops, relevant Statistical Methods are based on Clustering and Nearest Neighbour Analysis. Qualitative statements with market functions are concerned by the analytical results of the response to the questionnaires. According to these analyses, retail shops are clustered, particularly along the main roads and near the markets.

Research Design

There are five portions in this research paper. Firstly, part I is geographical factors to relate wards area along the Yangon-Mandaly Road within Bago City. Part II is defined the type of retail shops, the number of retail shops, distribution and functions of retail shops in the study area. Part III is analyzed of the transportation network from two major markets in Bago City. Part IV is analyzed the concentration and clustering of retail shops, relevant Statistical Methods are based on Clustering and Nearest Neighbour Analysis. Qualitative statements with market functions are concerned by the analytical results of the response to the questionnaires. Finally, it is comment and suggestion.

1. Geographical Factors

Physical Factors

Bago City is located in southern part of Bago Township and Bago Region (Figure1 and 2). Yangon-Mandaly Road within Bago City is located between 17° 14' N and 17° 21' N latitudes and 96° 27' E and 92° 30' E longitudes. Bago City is bounded by Warmayan, Mekhon, Okhpo village tracts on the north, Kamarnat, Hmontaing and Auksidee (West) village tracts on the east, Zaynyaungpin and Gwayttanshey village tracts on the southeast and Nyaungginn Village Tract on west. It constructed 31 wards. Among them 16 wards are constructed by the study area in the Bago City (Figure 3 and 4).

Figure 1
Location of Bago
Division in
Myanmar
 Source: Myanmar
 Survey
 Department

Figure 2 Location of
Bago Township within
Bago Division

Figure 3 Location of
Bago City in Bago
Township

Figure 4 Location of Retail
Shop along Yangon-Mandalay
Road in Bago City

Human Factors

In 1972, Bago City was 4,416 persons. In 1973, the population was increased by 123,586 and promote to 150,528 in 1983. In 1993, the number of population was become 185,249 and 224,795 in 2003 and 305,501 in 2013. The increase number 34,721 was 10 year between 1983 and 1993. The increase number 80,706 was 10 year between 1993 and 2003.

The study area was 173036 persons which presented 56.6 percent of the Bago City (305,501 persons) in 2013. In 2014, study area was decreased 101893 persons or 42.9 percent of the Bago City (237619persons). The decrease number was 71143 within one year from 2013 to 2014. In 2018, study area was 85668 persons or 43.5 percent of the Bago City (196927 persons). Further decrease number 16225 was 5 years between 2014 and 2018.

Continuous decrease number within 5 years was due to emigration to other places such as neighbor regions and state in Myanmar and abroad for better job opportunity and earning greater income of the study area and Bago City.

Population Distribution

The study area is unevenly distributed in population in 2013. The high crowded wards were Myothit, Kyunthayar , Zaigganaing North and Oktha (7) in 2013. It was transferred to Oktha (8), Kyunthayar and Myothit in 2014. The study area was evenly distributed in 2018 in Figure 5.

Bago City is unevenly distributed in population in 2013. The high crowded wards were Myothit, Nandawyar and Mazin (7) in 2013. It was transferred to Nandawyar, Mazin and Oktha (8) in 2014. Bago City was more crowded area was Nandawyar Ward and other wards were evenly distributed in 2018 in Figure 6.

Generally, population distribution was revealed northern most direction of the study area and Bago City in 2013. In 2014 and 2018, the population distribution was inversed to southern most direction or toward the Yangon Region in the study and Bago City. According to gravity theory, it is pulled to big city or Yangon City.

Figure 5 Population Distribution in Study Area (2018)

Figure 6 Population Distribution

Population Density

The study area was 4895 per square kilometer in 2013 and decreased 2882 per square kilometer in 2014, decreased to 2423 persons per square kilometre in 2018.

The study area with wards by relatively highest population density was Kyaukkyisu (62016), Myothit (60662) and Zaiggaing North (34591) by per square kilometre in 2013.

In the study area, most concentration wards were Nyaungwaing South (92596), Zaypine (92308) and Panhlaing (67087) by per square in 2018 (Figure 7).

Wards by Bago City with relatively highest population density were Mazin (67993), Kyaukkyisu (62016) and Myothit (60662) by per square kilometre in 2013.

In the Bago City, most concentration wards are Nyaungwaing South (92596), Zaypine (92308) and Panhlaing (67087) by per square in 2018 in Figure 8.

Generally, the highest population concentration area was variation both in study area and Bago city between 2013 and 2018. Moreover, the wards with accessibility and near Bago Myoma Market are highly concentrated that has a large number of commercial activities.

In the Bago City, lowest concentration wards were Oktha (9) (343), Oktha (8) (694), and Oktha (7) (1340) by per square in 2018.

Generally, the lowest population concentration wards with accessibility and far from the Bago Myoma Market but there are highly concentrated that has a large number of retail shops. All Oktha Myothit wards are with large area but there are low population density because which is being a newly settle area.

Figure 7 Population Density in Study Area (2018)

Figure 8 Population Density in Bago City (2018)

2. Spatial Distribution of Retail Shops and Markets

Types of Retail Shops

The shops included in the retail activity are classified into 7 Types. These are: (1) food and beverage shops, (2) grocery (miscellaneous) shops, (3) personal and household goods shops, (4) textile and garment shops, (5) construction material shops, (6) service businesses and (7) other shops. The varieties of shops included in each type are:

The varieties of shops included in each type are in Table 1.

Table 1 Types and Numbers of Retail Shops along Yangon – Mandalay Road of Bago City (2017)

No.	Types	Shops	Percent
1	Food and Beverage Shops	216	31.58
2	Grocery (Miscellaneous) Shops	86	12.57
3	Personal and Household Goods Shops	82	11.99
4	Textile and Garment Shops	25	3.65
5	Construction Material Shops	25	3.65
6	Services Businesses	191	27.92
7	Other Shops	59	8.63
Total		684	100

Source: Field Survey (June to August 2017)

Distribution of Retail Shops in the Wards

Bago City comprises of 31 wards and out of 15 wards is the study area with the number of retail shops is 684. Kyuntharyar Ward ranks first in the number of retail shops with 128 in number which represent 18.71 percent of the total, followed by Oktha (8) Ward with 91 in number 13.3 percent and Oktha (7) Ward with 90 shops 13.16 percent. Oktha (2) Ward has the least number of retail shops with only 1 in number 0.15 percent. The large number of retail shops in Kyuntharyar Ward is due to the presence of Myoma Market which is the largest among the markets in Bago City. The extremely small number of retail shops in Oktha (2) Ward is on due to being close to Myoma Market but it was cornered small area in Yangon – Mandalay Road within Bago City.

In Hanthawaddy Ward, there are 35 retail shops 5.12 percent of which Type 1 shops are the largest in number 21 shops and Type 4 shops are only 1 in number type. There are no type 5 shops and Type 6 shops in the ward.

The number of retail shops in Kyuntharyar Ward is 128 (18.71 percent) of which Type 6 ranks first with 42 shops and Type 5 shops are only 4 in number type but there are all type of shops.

There are 4 retail shops 0.58 percent in Myodwingyi Ward which is second least ranks in the number of retail shops among the 15 wards. Type 1 shops are the greatest in number with 3 and it has no shop of Type 3, 4, 5, 6 and 7.

Myothit Ward has 48 retail shops 7.02 percent and it is trend to east direction or toward the Mandalay. Type shop ranks first with 15 shops among the 6 Types in this ward. Besides, the wards are locationally adjoined with the rural area where vegetables and other crops are intensively grown for the urban markets.

The number of retail shops in Nyaungwaing South Ward is 16 (2.34 percent) of which Type 2 and 3 shops are the most common with 5 shops of each but no Type 4 and 5 shops.

There are 1 retail shops 0.15 percent in Oktha (2) Ward and Type 2 to 7 shops are no shops.

Oktha (4) Ward has 44 retail shops 6.43 percent of which Type 6 shops are the most common with 12 shops.

In Oktha (6) Ward, the number of retail shops is 15 (2.19 percent) of which Type 6 shops are the most common with 5 shops, but the ward has no Type 4 shop.

Oktha (7) Ward has 90 retail shops 13.16 percent of which 31 are of Type 1 shops and 30 shops of Type 7 shop.

Oktha (8) Ward, the number of retail shops is the second largest among the 15 wards with 91 retail shops 13.3 percent of which Type 1 shops are the most common with 30 shops and but there are 28 shops of Type 7.

Oktha (9) Ward has 89 retail shops 13.01 percent of which 51 shops are Type 1 and the ward has 1 shop in Type 5 shop.

Yonegyi Ward has 26 retail shops 3.8 percent and Type 3 is the most common with 12 shops and it has no Type 5 shop.

Zaiggaing North Ward, there are 47 retail shops 6.87 percent and Type 1 rank first with 24 shops but the ward has no Type 3, 4 and 5 shop.

There are 86 retail shops in Htaukkyant Junction Ward of which Type 6 ranks first with 11 shops, but there is no Type 5 shop.

Zaypine Ward has 31 retail shops 4.53 percent and Type 6 ranks first with 13 shops. The ward has 1 shop in Type 5 shop.

There are 19 retail shops 2.78 percent in Panhlaing Ward of which Type 3 and Type 6 ranks first with 5 shops for each and the ward has no Type 5 (Table 2 and Figure 9).

Table 2 The Functional Retail Shops in Yangon – Mandalay Road of Bago City (2017)

No	Ward	Food and Beverage Shops	Grocery Shops	Personal and Household Goods Shops	Textile and Garment Shops	Construction Material Shops	Services Businesses	Other Shops	Total	Percent
1	Hanthawaddy	21	3	3	1	0	7	0	35	5.12
2	Kyuntharyar	29	19	16	6	4	42	12	128	18.71
3	Myodwingyi	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	4	0.58
4	Myothit	12	8	2	1	2	15	8	48	7.02
5	Nyaungwaing South	2	5	5	0	0	4	0	16	2.34
6	Oktha (2)	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.15
7	Oktha (4)	10	5	6	1	4	12	6	44	6.43
8	Oktha (6)	3	3	1	0	1	5	2	15	2.19
9	Oktha (7)	31	8	8	3	3	30	7	90	13.16
10	Oktha (8)	30	11	7	2	9	28	4	91	13.30
11	Oktha (9)	51	9	4	3	1	15	6	89	13.01
12	Yonegyi	6	2	12	1	0	4	1	26	3.80
13	Zaiggaing North	9	9	7	4	0	11	7	47	6.87
14	Zaypine	4	2	6	3	1	13	2	31	4.53
15	Panhlaing	4	1	5	0	0	5	4	19	2.78
Total		216	86	82	25	25	191	59	684	100

Source: Field Survey (June to August 2017)

Spatial Distribution of Markets in the Study Area

There are 2 markets in Yangon – Bago – Mandalay Road. These are Myoma Market and Pyinsi Market. The total number of retail shops in the 2 markets is 1062, of which 838 or 78.91 percent are located in Myoma Market which is the largest in Bago City and number of shops with 224 which account for only 21.09 percent of the Pyisi Market.

Myoma Market is located at Yonegyi Ward in Yangon – Bago – Mandalay Road and it has 838 shops which account for first ranking is Textile and Garment Shops (T4), 439 shop or 52.4 percent of the total are the most dominant as a result of proximity to the rural area rather than urban. Ranking second is Grocery (Miscellaneous) Shops (T2) is 158 shop or 18.9 percent of the total. This also accounts for the number of Type 3 shops with only 147 (17.5 percent).

Type 1 shop with 54 (6.4 percent) whereas Type 6 shops are 19 shops (2.3 percent), Construction Material Shops 18 shops or 2.1 percent and likewise the least in number with only 3 shops 0.4 percent in the total shops.

Figure 9 The Distributions of Retail Shops along Yangon – Mandalay Road within Bago City (2017)

Source: Based on Table 2

Pyinsi Market is located in Oktha (8) Ward and it has 224 shops. Grocery (Miscellaneous) Shops (Type 2) 120 retail shops which represent 3.28 % of the total. Type 2 shops with 34 in number 174 or 77.7 percent are the most common in the market, whereas Type 6 shops are the least with only 1 shop or 0.4 percent. For Food and Beverage Shops (Type 1) 41 shops are the second largest number, but Type 5 and Type 7 shop has no shop. Type 3 and Type 4 has the small number of shops in total (Table 3 and Figure 10).

Table 3 Markets in Yangon – Bago – Mandalay Road in the Study Area

No.	Types	No. of Shops	No. of Shops
1	Food and Beverage Shops	54	41
2	Grocery (Miscellaneous) Shops	158	174
3	Personal and Household Goods Shops	147	5
4	Textile and Garment Shops	439	3
5	Construction Material Shops	18	0
6	Services Businesses	19	1
7	Other Shops	3	0
Total		838	224

Source: Department of Market in Myoam and Pyinsi Markets

Figure 10 Spatial Distributions of Markets in the Study Area

Source: Based on Table 3

3. Economic Factors

Marketing Function

The retail shops in study area buy the items for sale from their respective townships and from major markets of Bago and Yangon. These major markets have different kinds of commodities that come from Bago Myoma Market, Yangon, Company, Nantawyar Market and others. Sale items buy from Bago Myoma Market with shops 277 or 40.50 percent of total retail shops of 684 in the study area. Yangon is the second large buy the sale items with 174 shops or 25.44 percent of total shop 684 in the study area. Sale items buy third market is Nantawyar Market with 115 shops or 16.81 percent of the total shops 684 in the study area in Table 4 and Figure 12. Other markets buy the sale items within the Bago Region such as Bandargone, Intakaw, Pyinsi Market, Phayargyi, Nyaunglaypin, Kyaunggyisu, Taungoo, Tharyaraye and Waw and more distance markets such as Belin, Htaukkyant, Khayan, Myaingan, Myawady, Muse, Myitkinar, Kyaukpandaung, Shwebo and China (steel item) in Table 4 and Figure 11.

Table 4 Sale Items Buy from the Major Market

Sale Items Buy From the Market	Shop	Percent
Bago Myoma Market	277	40.50
Bago Myoma Market and Yangon	11	1.61
Bago Myoma Market and Company	6	0.88
Company, Bago Myoma Market and Yangon	51	7.46
Company	13	1.90
Company and Yangon	18	2.63
Garden	6	0.88
Nantawyar Market	115	16.81
Yangon	174	25.44
Other	13	1.90
Total	684	100

Source: Field Survey (June to August 2017)

Figure 11 Sale Items Buy from the Major Market

Source: Based on Table 4

Retailers' behavior

Retailers, their selling items were influenced by most of factors such as location, main road, price, social and shop position.

Figure 12 show the customer's preference in buying of goods. About 20.47 percent of retailer answered Location. About 18.27 percent of retailer responded social and price. 17.4 percent of retailer expressed social and 9.35 percent price.

Figure 12 Customer's Preference in Buying Items

Source: Based on Table 5

Responds their shops construct brick building represent 53.95 percent of the total responds, while 135 (19.74 percent) use hart and 93 (13.6 percent) rick and wood used for shop structure in Table 5 and Figure 13. The categories of hart hops are included betel shop, cold drink shop, coffee shop, snack shop, fish pickle shop, footstall, fruit shop, melon shop, mohinga shop, and toddy palm shop.

Table 5 Shop Structure in the Study Area

Type	Shop	Percent
Brick	369	53.95
Brick and Wood	93	13.60
Hart	135	19.74
Wood	87	12.72
Total	684	100

Source: Field Survey (June to August 2017)

Figure 13 Shop Structure in the Study Area

Shop Area in the Study Area

According to questionnaires 684, out of 421 retailers or 61.55 percent spend less than 5 feet and 10 feet wide of their shop. There are usual types of shop in the study area. Figure 14 reveal that the number of shop wide. Generally, between 100 feet and 300 feet wide shops are coffee shop, garment industry, restaurant, hotel and motel, bamboo shop, brick, stone and sand, water boon playground, car showroom and purified drinking water shop. It is less than 2 percent or 7 shops in the study area.

Figure 14 Shop Area in the Study Area

Source: Based on Table 7

Customers' Behavior

Finally, sellers are asked about the estimate location of customer buying in their shops. Figure 16 show the variation of customer in the study area. Customers come about 17.11 percent from the same ward. 184 customers or 26.9 percent come from same ward and other ward. About 19.44 percent customers come from same ward, other ward and other township and 61 customers or 8.92 percent.

4. Spatial Analysis and Factors Affecting the Distribution Pattern of Retail Shops
Spatial Analysis on the Distribution Pattern of Retail Shops

Geospatial analysis utilizes many of these terms, other are drawn from disciplines such as mathematics and statistics. Uses of analysis are three types of analysis of retail shops in Kanthar Ward. They are Nearest Neighbour Analysis and Mapping Cluster Analysis

Nearest Neighbour Analysis

The Average Nearest Neighbour to measure the distance between each features centroid and its nearest neighbour's centroid location.

Note, however, that the statistical significance for the method is strongly impacted by study area Table 6. For the Average Nearest Neighbour statistic, the null hypothesis states that features are clustered distributed in Figure 15. For the distribution of retail shops in the urban area of Bago, the average nearest neighbour analysis is 0.55 which also lies within the limit of clustered pattern in Table 7.

Table 6 The Result of Spatial Distribution Pattern of Retail Shops

Item	Distance ratio	Significant level (percent)	Z score	P Value	Distribution
All Retail Shop	0.266829	99.99	- 36.870189	0.000000	Clustered

Source: Based on the Value of Nearest Neighbour Analysis Use by Arc GIS

Figure 15 Nearest Neighbour Analysis Result of Retail Shops along Yangon – Mandalay Road of Bago City (2017)

Source: Field Survey (June to August 2017)

Table 7 Seven Categories of Retail Shops along Yangon – Mandalay Road of Bago City (2017)

No.	Types	Shops	P value	Z score	Significant Level (Percent)	Pattern
1	Food and Beverage Shops	216	0.000000	- 22.151788	99.99	Clustered
2	Grocery (Miscellaneous) Shops	86	0.000000	- 13.346047	99.99	Clustered
3	Personal and Household Goods Shops	82	0.000000	- 11.094953	99.99	Clustered
4	Textile and Garment Shops	25	0.000091	- 3.914000	99.99	Clustered
5	Construction Material Shops	25	0.000559	- 3.450649	99.99	Clustered
6	Services Businesses	191	0.000000	6.908421	99.99	Dispersed
7	Other Shops	59	0.000000	54.781144	99.99	Dispersed
	All Type of Retail Shop	684	0.000000	- 36.870189	99.99	Clustered

Source: Field Survey (June to August 2017)

Bago City, retail shops are clustered around the markets and along the main roads. As mentioned earlier by dot method, people are clustering more around the markets. The Nearest Neighbour Analysis shows that retail shops are clustering where population concentration is high. The high clustering of retail shops along the main roads is due to high accessibility in Table 7.

Mapping Cluster Analysis

In order to show the degree of cluster from Hot Spot Analysis (Getis-Ord Gi) was also measured. Result of the above analysis showed that the distribution of retail shops in the study area is clustered form. In this area, the highest degree of cluster is Oktha (8), and Oktha (9) in the southern part of the study area and pull of the part of Yangon City. Second clustered area is Nyaungwaing South, Zaypine, Yonegyi and Kyunthayar in the urban core area. Low cluster area is in the northern part of the study area. The mean center is located in the Oktha (7) Ward and it is near the urban core area in Figure 16.

**Figure 16 Mapping Cluster Analysis along Yangon
– Mandalay Road of Bago City (2017)**

Source: Field Survey (June to August 2017)

In field survey time (June to August 2017), sell condition was the highest condition 65.35 percent in median condition, 24.12 percent in good condition, 1.75 percent in low condition and 8.77 percent was not responded of the study area.

Most of the retail shops were opened 259 shops or 37.87 percent after 2001, 237 shops or 34.65 percent between 1788 and 2001, 16 shops or 2.34 percent before 1988 and 172 shops or 25.15 percent was not responded in survey time (June to August 2017). Most of the people 271 persons or 39.62 percent were educated persons, 181 persons or 26.46 percent presented high school level, 68 persons or 9.94 percent in primary school level and 81 persons or 11.84 percent was not responded in field survey period (June to August 2017).

Finally, the study area founds the variation of shops types such as own and rent shops. About 78 percent or 533 shops are own shop, 3.95 percent or 27 shops in extension from Yangon and 1.61 percent or 11 shops extension from Bago City.

Suggestion

Being a road junction with wide productive farmland, it functions as a collecting and distribution centre of agricultural and manufactured products. This has enhanced the development of road links to different direction, in addition to the main road that proceeds to Mandalay and branches off to Mon State and Thanatharyi Region and Highway Road.

The construction of Bago Bridge (Bago) across the Bago River enhances under bridge could constructed the circuits road within Bago City the speedy flow of people and commodity to connect the Bago Myoma Market. Government Municipal Department was defined the boundary for Municipal Area and sell for retail shops.

Conclusions

Bago City, retail shops are clustered around the markets and along the main roads. The Nearest Neighbour Analysis shows that retail shops are clustering where population concentration is high. The high clustering of retail shops along the main roads is due to high accessibility. Low cluster area is in the northern part of the study area.

This area was constructed by roads and number of bridges which have been constructed up to the end of 2010. Selling items were transferred from restaurant to textile and garment shops near bridges.

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